

1 Submitted to Microporous and Mesoporous Materials

2
3 **CU OR FE-EXCHANGED NATURAL CLINOPTILOLITE AS A SUSTAINABLE PHOTO-FENTON CATALYST FOR**
4 **WATER DISINFECTION AT NEAR NEUTRAL pH**

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23 **ABSTRACT**

24 Natural clinoptilolite can be used to obtain effective catalysts for heterogeneous photo-Fenton type
25 reactions due to their low cost and their physicochemical properties that make them ideal for water
26 treatment. In this work, a natural zeolite (clinoptilolite) has been modified by incorporating iron (NZ-Fe)
27 and copper (NZ-Cu) as compensation cations, through simple and economical hydrothermal processes.
28 The adequate incorporation of iron and copper into the zeolite, as well as the structural stability of the
29 samples, were demonstrated through X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy
30 (FTIR), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). DR-UV-Vis measurements allowed the bandgap
31 estimation to predict the photocatalytic performance of both materials. Their effectivity in heterogeneous
32 photo-Fenton system was confirmed by evaluating the inactivation of *E. coli* as a model pathogen in water.
33 Bacterial detection limit (initial $\approx 10^6$ CFU/mL) was reached using 1 g/L of both catalysts, 100 ppm of H₂O₂
34 under visible light (410-710 nm / 9 W/m²) and near neutral pH in 2 hours of treatment, while no post-
35 treatment regrowth was observed. Experimental data were analysed according to three disinfection
36 kinetic models, Chick-Watson first-order, Weibull, and Hom models. While more hydroxyl radicals are
37 determined (trapping tests) in presence of NZ-Fe and less iron leachate is observed, when NZ-Cu is used,
38 good reusability is attained during three disinfection cycles. This makes copper-exchanged clinoptilolite a

39 suitable and low-cost photocatalyst for water disinfection through heterogeneous photo-Fenton type
40 processes.

41 **Keywords:** *natural zeolite, iron and copper exchange, heterogeneous photo-Fenton, visible light, E. coli*

42 **1. Introduction**

43 Microporous materials have a significant presence in solving relevant problems in a wide range of
44 applications. Concerning to water, there is a long experience in using zeolites and metal-organic
45 frameworks (MOFs) for ion-exchange and adsorption applications [1–3], which are based on their
46 fascinating structures. In contrast, the use of these materials in water contamination with pathogens has
47 been much less treated. However, this is an area that calls urgent attention as it is a significant problem
48 that affects millions of people worldwide. According to UN and WHO data, approximately 2.2 billion people
49 lack access to safe drinking water, and this deficiency is directly associated with the proliferation of
50 waterborne diseases such as cholera, diarrhoea, and typhoid fever [4]. The UN has established access to
51 clean water and sanitation as one of the Sustainable Development Goals, recognising the importance of
52 addressing this problem. The presence of pathogens in water is a key factor in perpetuating this global
53 health crisis, which requires urgent measures to ensure that all individuals have access to clean and safe
54 water, which will significantly contribute to the enhancement of public health and well-being worldwide.
55 In developing countries, water stress is intimately linked to water scarcity and the degradation of its quality
56 resulting from urban development and agriculture. In these regions, the reuse of treated water has been
57 well accepted as an imperative solution to address these challenges [5–7].

58 To achieve effective wastewater treatment, advanced methodologies are needed to surpass classical
59 treatments performed in urban wastewater treatment plants, which have been proven to be inefficient
60 for certain emerging contaminants [8]. Advanced oxidation processes are presented as alternatives
61 because of their ability to eliminate a wide range of contaminants, including persistent organic
62 compounds, heavy metals, and pathogens in water [9,10]. The photo-Fenton process stands out as one of
63 the best advanced oxidation processes. Its uniqueness lies in the generation of highly reactive hydroxyl
64 radicals through a photochemical reaction driven by ultraviolet radiation or sunlight, using only hydrogen
65 peroxide and an iron source [11]. Heterogeneous photo-Fenton treatment is a variant that involves
66 immobilising a photoactive iron specie on a solid, such as zeolites and silicas, among others [12], rather
67 than its soluble form (homogeneous photo-Fenton). This allows for greater catalyst reusability and
68 efficiency, along with extended lifespan compared to homogeneous systems. Furthermore, it reduces the
69 generation of ferrous sludge, which requires subsequent treatment and proper disposal, as seen in
70 homogeneous photo-Fenton treatment [13]. Consequently, in recent years, the heterogeneous photo-
71 Fenton process has emerged as a promising approach for the removal of pathogens and other
72 contaminants in wastewater [12,14]. The main disadvantages of the heterogeneous photo-Fenton process
73 are related to the selection of the appropriate solid catalyst and adaption of it to water conditions. With
74 certain catalysts, reactivity may be lower, potentially requiring longer residence times. Additionally, in
75 many cases, the synthesis and preparation of solid catalysts can be a more complex and costly process. In
76 a way to circumvent this situation, the identified challenges could be addressed by using solid catalysts
77 like those prepared from zeolitic minerals.

78 Zeolites can be excellent catalysts in the heterogeneous photo-Fenton process for several reasons: i)
79 possess a highly ordered three-dimensional microporous structure, providing them with a large surface
80 area that contains active sites for the suitable diffusion of contaminants, thus improving the efficiency of

81 the process [15]. ii) have the capability to exchange metal ions, such as iron, within their structure. This
82 enables the immobilization of iron ions in the zeolite, serving as catalysts in the photo-Fenton process [16].
83 iii) are well-known for their chemical stability under a wide range of conditions, making them suitable both
84 as intrinsic catalysts and as supports for catalysts in environmental applications [17]. This stability ensures
85 that zeolitic catalysts are durable and do not disintegrate during the water treatment process. iv) can be
86 easily regenerated and reused after the photo-Fenton process, reducing costs and minimising waste
87 generation, rendering them an essential tool for addressing water pollution challenges worldwide.

88 Synthetic zeolites are extensively utilized as in the heterogeneous Fenton process, either as supports or
89 having intrinsic photochemical properties [18–20]. However, its high cost is usually a handicap for its large-
90 scale usage. The application of natural zeolites as catalysts in heterogeneous photo-Fenton processes
91 offers significant advantages for sustainability. Moreover, natural zeolites possess the same beneficial
92 physicochemical properties as synthetic zeolites [12,21], when the pore size is not a restriction, since most
93 natural zeolites have small pores. Implementing natural materials in this context not only optimizes the
94 process of contaminant removal in water but also promotes more eco-friendly and economical practices
95 in environmental treatments. Fukuchi *et al.* demonstrated that Fe-natural clinoptilolite was not active per
96 se for the decontamination of 2,4,6-tribromophenol via a Fenton process, while the addition of reducing
97 agents such as ascorbic acid or hydroxylamine does achieve complete degradation [21]. Recently, heavily
98 dealuminated hierarchical natural clinoptilolite exchanged with iron has been applied as heterogeneous
99 Fenton catalyst for the treatment of biologically treated domestic sewage to remove diclofenac and
100 ranitidine, but simvastatin was not possible to remove [22]. Due to the large dealumination and the
101 presence of mesopores, this modified clinoptilolite contains iron as exchangeable cations and forming
102 oxide nanoparticles in the mesoporosity, which have shown an active role in the Fenton process. The
103 inability of the catalyst to remove simvastatin was explained by the inaccessibility of the molecule to the
104 microporosity due to its size. We must note that diclofenac and ranitidine although have smaller size than
105 simvastatin they are large enough to enter into the clinoptilolite microporosity and might access only to
106 the created mesoporosity. Phan et al. prepared a material by calcining at 700 °C of a mixture of natural
107 clinoptilolite and lanthanum iron oxide (at 15, 30 and 60 wt.%) for photo-Fenton degradation of rhodamine
108 [23]. The clinoptilolite without LaFeO₃ adsorbed 30% of the dye in the dark, while a further 10% is removed
109 by the action of the light. In contrast, the composites have a marginal adsorption of rhodamine and on
110 degrade the dye in light to an extent very similar to that of the oxide, indicating that the photocatalytic
111 activity is not provided by the clinoptilolite used [23].

112 The literature cited above encourages research into the use of natural clinoptilolite as a catalyst in photo-
113 Fenton disinfection of water. However, there are open questions that should be addressed: Would the
114 clinoptilolite ion-exchanged with appropriate extra-framework cations be photoactive? Is ion-exchanged
115 clinoptilolite sufficient for photo-Fenton processes or do other catalysts need to be in place? If the metal-
116 exchanged clinoptilolite showed photoactivity to generate $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals from H₂O₂, would they be produced
117 in sufficient quantity and time to be used for disinfection? If disinfection is achieved, is bacterial
118 inactivation effective or does regrowth occur after treatment? Can the metal-exchanged clinoptilolite be
119 reused in disinfection processes? It should be noted that, to our knowledge, natural zeolites have not been
120 used for the inactivation of pathogens in waters by heterogeneous photo-Fenton systems.

121 In the present work, heterogeneous catalysts based on a natural clinoptilolite exchanged with iron and
122 copper cations were evaluated for water disinfection using *E. coli* as model bacterium by photo-Fenton
123 under visible light. The characterization of the materials was carried out to confirm the incorporation of

124 iron and copper and the structural stability of the modified zeolites. DR-UV-Vis measurements allowed the
125 bandgap to be determined to predict the photocatalytic performance of both materials. Their effectivity
126 was experimentally evaluated in water disinfection *E. coli* and the kinetics of the reaction, the generation
127 of hydroxyl radicals during the reaction were determined via trapping tests, as well as the reuse capacity
128 of the catalysts were analysed.

129 **2. Materials and Methods**

130 *2.1. Preparation of the zeolitic materials*

131 The starting material used was the natural zeolite from the Tasajeras deposit (Cuba). The mineral was
132 sieved and the fraction with particle size between 40-90 μm was purified by successive washings with
133 distilled water at room and boiling temperature to remove accompanying phases. The purified zeolite was
134 denoted as NZ and consists of a mixture of clinoptilolite (70%), mordenite (5%), anorthite (15%) and quartz
135 (10%) [24].

136 An acid sample of NZ was prepared by ion exchange with ammonium chloride (highly favoured in
137 clinoptilolite), followed by calcination at 450 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 hours. Iron-enriched (NZ-Fe) and copper-enriched
138 (NZ-Cu) samples were prepared by ion exchange of the acid NZ, with the aim of achieving a high degree of
139 exchange [25]. In all the ion exchange processes, a concentration of 0.5 M of the corresponding salt (NH_4Cl ,
140 FeSO_4 and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$) was used, performing three exchange cycles of 4-hour at a temperature of 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and
141 a solid/liquid ratio of 1g/10mL. After the last exchange the samples were washed repeatedly with distilled
142 water to remove excess salt and allowed to dry in an oven at 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The prepared materials and also those
143 after the photocatalytic tests were characterized by using X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform
144 Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), UV-Vis spectroscopy (UV-Vis), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM/EDX).
145 Details are shown in the *Supplementary Information*.

146 *2.2. E. coli inactivation by zeolites assisted photo-Fenton*

147 *E. coli* strain K12 was used as model to evaluate the catalytic activity of the zeolitic materials. The
148 preparation of the microorganism stock and the inoculum are described in the supplementary information.
149 For the photo-Fenton tests saline solution (0.9 % w/v NaCl) with an initial concentration of *E. coli* of 10^6
150 CFU/mL, 100 ppm (2.9 mM) of H_2O_2 , and 1 g/L of the zeolitic catalyst were used at pH close to neutrality
151 (approximately 6 without external adjustment). A double-jacketed glass 1L reactor with water
152 recirculation was used for testing (Figure S1). It was operated at a constant temperature of 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and with
153 magnetic stirring at 500 rpm. The reactor was covered with aluminium foil to improve and re-distribute
154 light inside the reactor, and radiation was delivered by a submerged visible light lamp (410-710 nm / 9
155 W/m^2 , submerged length 21 cm). Experiments were also carried out using an UVA submerged lamp
156 (374nm / 29 W/m^2) (results in supplementary information). The emission spectra of the lamps are shown
157 in Figure S2.

158 The reactor was filled with the saline solution and a control sample was taken to verify the absence of
159 microorganisms in both, reactor and solution. An overnight *E. coli* culture in LB (10^9 CFU/mL) was
160 centrifuged and washed to eliminate residual culture medium and used to inoculate the reactor. Then,
161 after stirring for homogenisation, a sample was collected to determine the initial concentration of bacteria
162 for each experiment. A 'dark-control' sample was taken and kept in the dark at room temperature and
163 plated twice, at start and end of the experiment, to confirm the correct viability of the bacteria in the
164 saline solution during the tests. Subsequently, zeolitic material and/or hydrogen peroxide were added in
165 dark. After homogenization of the system, the reactor was exposed to the radiation source and samples
166 were taken at predetermined times for 2 h. To quench the action of H_2O_2 over bacteria during the time

167 interval between sampling and plating, the sample was mixed with the required amount of catalase
168 solution. The experiments were done in triplicate; the results did not show significant statistical variations
169 (confidence level > 95%). Once each treatment is finished (at 2 h), a 'final-control' sample is reserved and
170 plated twice at the sampling time and 24 h after to evaluate any potential bacterial regrowth. After each
171 treatment the reactor is thoroughly cleaned with sodium hypochlorite 50 % v/v and then washed three
172 times with distilled water. Additionally, all materials and prepared solutions were sterilised by autoclaving
173 at 1 bar, 121°C for 20 min.

174 Solution samples taken during the experiment were enumerated using the standard plate counting
175 method through 10-fold serial dilutions in LB. Colonies were counted after 24 h incubation at 37 °C. This
176 procedure was carried out in triplicate for each sample. The detection limit was 50 CFU/mL.

177 To study the reuse of the catalysts, three consecutive cycles of disinfection of the microorganism were
178 carried out with the same zeolitic material, following the procedure and conditions previously described.

179 To evaluate the disinfection process, the kinetics of the bacterial inactivation was studied. Details are
180 accessible in the *Supplementary Information*. In connection with an in-depth understanding of the catalytic
181 processes, tests were conducted to see in which extent the hydroxyl radical are the key elements and also
182 the metal ions leached into the solutions (see details in the *Supplementary Information*).

183

184 **3. Results and Discussion**

185

186 *3.1. Characterization of NZ, NZ-Fe and NZ-Cu*

187 NZ shows lamellar crystals with smooth edges, which are stacked in the mineral, giving compact aggregates
188 of about 90 µm, as can be seen in the SEM images (Figure 1). No significant changes in the morphology are
189 observed in the prepared NZ-Fe and NZ-Cu samples. The morphology of the zeolite also does not change
190 after the photo-Fenton tests, but elongated particles containing mostly sodium and chlorine appear due
191 to the reaction medium employed in the disinfection assays (NaCl 0.9%). As expected, no iron or copper
192 oxides or hydroxides particles were found in the micrographs, since the employed method assures the
193 exchange of both cations in natural clinoptilolite rather than the precipitation of other phases [25]. The
194 elemental chemical composition, reported in Table 1, confirmed that the percentage of iron increased
195 from 1.81 to 8.92 %, while copper (absent in natural zeolite) is incorporated by approximately 5 % due to
196 the ion exchange. It was also demonstrated that Fe and Cu cations exchange with Na cations during the
197 photo-Fenton disinfection experiments, as will be discussed later.

198

199
 200 **Figure 1.** SEM micrographs of the natural zeolite and the samples enriched in iron and copper before and
 201 after photo-Fenton assays.

202
 203 **Table 1:** Elemental chemical composition (at. %) determined by EDX of NZ and the prepared catalysts
 204 before (NZ-Fe and NZ-Cu) and after (NZ-Fe and NZ-Cu post vis) photo-Fenton tests.
 205

Sample	Si	Al	Na	K	Ca	Mg	Fe	Cu	Cl	S
NZ	73.53	14.04	2.78	1.95	5.74	0.14	1.81	0.00	0.00	0.00
NZ-Fe	72.53	15.58	0.00	0.54	0.80	0.43	8.92	0.00	0.00	1.19
NZ-Fe post vis	73.24	14.70	3.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.13	0.00	2.38	0.00
NZ-Cu	76.12	15.53	0.00	0.73	0.66	0.00	2.01	4.94	0.00	0.00
NZ-Cu post vis	71.79	13.93	8.22	0.64	0.57	0.00	1.40	1.16	2.30	0.00

207 The normalised X-ray diffraction patterns of the parent natural zeolite (NZ) and the Fe and Cu exchanged
 208 samples (NZ-Fe and NZ-Cu) are shown in Figure 2A. The pattern of NZ confirms that clinoptilolite and
 209 mordenite are the main zeolitic phases presents. It can be verified that the method used to obtain the
 210 samples enriched in iron and copper as well as the photo-Fenton tests with visible and UVA light (see
 211 Figure S3) do not affect the zeolitic structure. Variations in the relative intensities of some reflections are
 212 only observed, due to changes in the occupancy, both nature and population, of the extra-framework
 213 cationic sites [25,26].

214 The FT-IR spectra of the zeolitic samples are shown in Figure 2B. The most intense band at 1056 cm^{-1} in
 215 NZ, shifts to 1067 and 1074 cm^{-1} in NZ-Cu and NZ-Fe, respectively. This band is associated with external
 216 tetrahedral asymmetric stretching, and its shift to a higher wavenumber could be due to an average
 217 increase in the T–O bond strength. The Al–O tetrahedral bond is weaker than Si–O bond, therefore
 218 differences in the Si/Al ratio of the zeolite can modify the frequency of the vibration. The observed shift
 219 to higher wavenumber may indicate that some dealumination of NZ occurred during the procedures
 220 carried out to obtain the exchanged samples, mainly during the obtaining of the acid form. These observed
 221 changes in the 1056 cm^{-1} bands are not expected to be caused by the presence of the transition metals, as
 222 they have been shown to be insensitive to this in clinoptilolite [27,28]. On the other hand, no significant
 223 changes are observed in the spectra of the samples after being used in disinfection tests (see Figure S4).

224 **Figure 2.** XRD powder patterns (A), FT-IR spectra (B), UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectra (C) and Tauc plots
 225 for n exponents of 1/2 and 2 (D) of natural zeolite (NZ) and samples exchanged with iron (NZ-Fe) and
 226 copper (NZ-Cu). Simulated patterns of clinoptilolite (CLI) and mordenite (MOR) reported by the
 227

228 *International Zeolite Association*, are also shown for comparison. Peaks that change their relative
229 intensities are indicated with asterisks.

230
231 Figure 2C shows the diffuse reflectance UV-vis spectra of the starting zeolite and the samples exchanged
232 with iron and copper cations. The spectrum of NZ shows four bands at 265, 360, 500 and 740 nm. Synthetic
233 clinoptilolite does not adsorb for $\lambda > 300$ nm, therefore the bands observed above this value are due to
234 impurities present in the mineral [29]. The band at 265 nm corresponds to oxygen bound to the aluminium
235 framework and is also assigned to the p-d charge transfer transition between the oxygen of the framework
236 and the iron cation [30]. The 360 nm band is assigned to octahedral Fe^{3+} in small Fe_2O_3 clusters, while the
237 500 nm band is associated with large Fe_2O_3 particles [31,32]. It has been reported that the band around
238 740 nm may be due to Fe^{2+} transitions or Fe^{2+} - Fe^{3+} inter-valence charge transfer [33,34]. The presence of
239 iron in natural zeolite (Table 1) may explain high absorption in the UV region and the presence of
240 absorption bands in the visible region. The absorbance of all bands increases after the iron exchange
241 process (sample NZ-Fe) and the bands at 500 and 740 nm shift to lower wavelength values (480 and 650
242 nm).

243 In the NZ-Cu sample, the band at 215 nm is associated with a charge-transfer complex, due to the
244 interaction of Cu^{2+} ions with ligand water molecules and/or with the zeolite framework [35]. The band at
245 260 nm corresponds to the overlapping of oxygen bonded to framework aluminium and Cu^{2+} species
246 interacting with oxygen from the zeolite structure. On the other hand, the bands in the wavelength range
247 from 300 to 500 nm correspond to the presence of copper in the form of Cu_xO [35]. Finally, the broad band
248 of about 800 nm can be attributed to Cu^{2+} cations in octahedral coordination [36,37].

249 The band gap energy (E_g) of the samples was estimated using the Tauc plot method followed the
250 procedure reported by Makula *et al.* [38]. The graphs for the allowed direct ($n = \frac{1}{2}$) and allowed indirect
251 ($n = 2$) transitions for each sample are shown in Figure 2D while the E_g values are summarised in Table 1S.
252 A significant reduction of band gap of NZ with respect to the theoretical value of $E_g = 5.593$ eV reported
253 for an idealised clinoptilolite is observed [39]. This is due to the presence of iron phases impurities in the
254 mineral, as mentioned above. Incorporation of iron and copper in NZ lowers the band gap energy of the
255 catalysts for the indirect transition. This may be due to the inhibition of the electron-hole recombination
256 process by introducing trap levels between the valence and conduction bands [40]. Recent work has
257 reported E_g values for different charged iron oxide clinoptilolite composites ranging from 2.08 eV to 1.88
258 eV ($n = \frac{1}{2}$) and 3.08 to 2.44 ($n = 2$) from 4.1 % to 13 % of FeO [41]. Also, recently Nippes *et al.* synthesised
259 a heterogeneous solid iron catalyst with commercial zeolite Y and obtained an estimated band gap energy
260 value of 2.95 eV [42]. All these E_g values are higher than those obtained for the NZ-Fe sample prepared by
261 ion exchange (see Figure 1D). For CuO supported on clinoptilolite Amiri and Nezamzadeh-Ejehieh [43]
262 reported a band gap of 2.8 eV, which is higher than the band gap energy of bulk CuO (1.2 - 1.5 eV).
263 However, the authors found that the supported CuO shows an improvement in its photocatalytic activity.
264 Also Zhang *et al.* [44], calculated a band gap of 2.16 eV for a synthesized Cu-based zeolite (Cu^0/CuZ) with
265 nanoparticles of copper and copper oxide and sodium as exchangeable cation. Our results confirm the
266 optical properties of NZ-Fe and NZ-Cu, since the estimated band gap energy values guarantee the ability
267 to absorb light in the visible region and consequently their application under solar radiation with high
268 effectiveness.

269 3.2. *E. coli* inactivation by NZ-Fe/Cu & Vis - assisted photo-Fenton: Reusability and kinetics

270 Figure 3A shows the results of the photo-Fenton inactivation of *E. coli* using the zeolitic catalysts under
271 visible light. As can be seen in the control assays, NZ-Fe and NZ-Cu zeolites in the absence of peroxide and
272 light showed no bacterial inactivation. Some reports in the literature account to the use of copper
273 exchanged zeolite as microbicide [45–47]. However, in our study, under the employed conditions, Cu^{+2} ion

274 exchanged in the zeolite is not responsible of the inactivation of *E. coli*, since the bacteria was viable
 275 (culturable) for the entire period of the experiment (Figure 3A). Also, there is no bacterial inactivation
 276 when only visible light (or UVA; Figure S5) is applied. This result is in concordance with previous studies
 277 [48] where the visible-induced inactivation of this bacteria was negligible independently of the applied
 278 irradiance (50-400 W/m²). As expected, addition of H₂O₂ did not exert any reduction on the bacteria
 279 population. Ginnaskis *et al.* [49], found two main categories of H₂O₂ concentrations: low concentration (1–
 280 3 mM) where internal damage occurs and high concentration (> 20 mM) where external damage occurs
 281 due to the action of the oxidant. In this study, a H₂O₂ concentration of 100 ppm (2.9 mM) is added to the
 282 system, so it would be in the low concentration range and oxidant addition is not expected to induce cell
 283 damage. However, the combination of light and H₂O₂ causes a slight inactivation (1-log) at 120 minutes. In
 284 the presence of UV and visible light there must be a substantial change. Several authors demonstrated
 285 that small amounts of H₂O₂ (0.015 – 1.5 mM) and solar radiation have a synergistic and lethal effect over
 286 resistant water microorganisms. For example, fungal spores were successfully inactivated in surface water
 287 [50], antimicrobial resistant *E. coli* in wastewater [51], total coliforms, *E. coli*, *Salmonella* spp., and
 288 *Enterococcus* spp. in real wastewater [52] and multidrug resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in urban
 289 wastewater [53].

290 This synergistic effect can be explained because first, the cell is damaged by the oxidative attack of
 291 hydrogen peroxide on the cell membrane, initiating the chain of lipid peroxidation that increases the
 292 permeability of the membrane, compromising the viability of the bacteria. On the other hand, the cell
 293 partially damaged by this oxidative attack is subjected to photo-absorption (UV and/or visible radiation),
 294 which produces greater bacterial inactivation [54]. Inactivation is complete when UVA is applied in
 295 combination with H₂O₂ (Figure S5). This could be due to the fact that the enzymes with antioxidant activity
 296 can be inactivated under UVA radiation, allowing the intracellular Fenton reaction to initiate. Therefore,
 297 H₂O₂ penetration and UVA exposure weaken the defences of bacteria, leading to greater inactivation [55].

299 **Figure 3.** Inactivation of *E. coli* (A) and consecutive cycles of *E. coli* inactivation (B and C) by photo-Fenton
300 with visible light using the zeolitic catalysts. The error bars were calculated from three independent
301 counting of bacteria colonies. DL (detection limit) = 50 CFU/mL.

302 When both zeolitic catalysts are used in visible photo-Fenton assays, complete inactivation of the bacteria
303 (up to the detection limit of the method used) is achieved within two hours (Figure 3A). It has been
304 reported that in the photocatalytic disinfection mechanism, reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated upon
305 irradiation of the catalyst cause bacterial inactivation by partial breakdown of the external membrane,
306 which allows ROS to reach the cell wall and cytoplasmic membrane, resulting in cell lysis. Thus, bacteria
307 are inactivated as a consequence of the cumulative effects of serial attacks by ROS on the cell wall-
308 membrane system [56]. Furthermore, no bacterial regrowth occurred within 24 h (data not shown),
309 suggesting that internal repair mechanisms such as enzyme induction (peroxidase, catalase, etc.) for DNA
310 repair by scavenging ROS do not occur, and that photo-Fenton treatment with both materials cause
311 irreversible damage to bacteria. On the other hand, when natural clinoptilolite is added without iron or
312 copper exchange, but in the presence of hydrogen peroxide and radiation, the inactivation is almost
313 negligible. This shows that the photo-Fenton reaction only occurs when the exchanged clinoptilolites are
314 used and that the natural zeolite has no photocatalytic activity under the conditions tested, as previously
315 reported [23]. The disinfection curves show different shapes depending on the metal cation exchanged
316 (Figure 3A). Three different regions can be identified in the plot for NZ-Fe zeolite, an initial delay, a smooth
317 decay up to 75 minutes, and a linear decrease with higher velocity towards the end of the experiment.
318 This behaviour suggests an initial superficial mechanism that may be due to sub-lethal damage to the
319 bacterial cell membrane. For NZ-Cu catalyst the initial delay is not observed, instead, an almost linear
320 decrease in the *E. coli* concentration as a function of time is observed from the beginning, with the
321 detection limit being reached at a slightly shorter time. This catalyst appears to cause more severe damage
322 to the cell membrane from the start of irradiation, leading to faster inactivation kinetics. Results in control
323 performed using this zeolite in absence of hydrogen peroxide demonstrated that the bacteria viability is
324 not affected by NZ-Cu alone as commented before. Therefore, it could be due to the volumetric rate and
325 the type of ROS generated in each case.

326 Three consecutive disinfection cycles were performed using the same catalyst to evaluate its reusability.
327 The results are shown in Figures 3B and 3C. When the iron catalyst is used in a second cycle, the shape of
328 the curve is similar, bacterial inactivation is observed but the detection limit is not reached within two
329 hours of the test. In a third cycle, practically no inactivation activity is observed. The copper catalyst
330 continues to be effective up to three photo-Fenton cycles, reaching the detection limit in all cases,
331 although at a slightly longer time. The fact that complete inactivation was found after the third cycle is a
332 very good result in terms of reducing the cost of catalyst application. It is interesting to note that the
333 amount of metal cation that leaves the catalysts after the three disinfection cycles is 31 % in the case of
334 iron and 76 % in the case of copper (see Table 1) which could be attributed to the higher solubility of Cu(II)
335 ion than Fe(III) species in the water at neutral pH [57]. This shows that even a very small amount of copper
336 is enough to produce the active species needed to inactivate the bacteria with practically the same
337 effectiveness.

338 The experimental kinetic data were analysed according to the Chick-Watson first order equation, the
339 Weibull model and the Hom model. The results are shown in Table 2 and Figure 4. As mentioned above,
340 the inactivation curve has an initial delay, commonly known as a shoulder, when the NZ-Fe catalyst is used.
341 This shoulder may be due to the fact that it takes time for the bacterial cells to show the effect of the
342 damage caused by the stress. Subsequently, this phase is followed by a linear decay until the detection
343 limit is reached. The experimental data for this sample best fitted the Weibull model, which, unlike the
344 Chick-Watson model, considers the delay in disinfection. In the case of the NZ-Cu catalyst, a decrease in

345 bacterial concentration is observed practically from the beginning of the photo-Fenton process and
 346 consequently the experimental data fits better to the Chick-Watson model.

347

348 **Table 2:** Kinetic parameters of the experimental data fitted according to different models.
 349

System	Chick-Watson model		Hom model			Weibull model		
	K_{max} (min^{-1})	R^2	K' (min^{-h})	h	R^2	Δ	p	R^2
NZ-Fe	0.18 ± 0.02	0.9143	$1 \times 10^{-6} \pm 2 \times 10^{-6}$	3.4 ± 0.4	0.9571	58 ± 5	3.4 ± 0.5	0.9572
NZ-Cu	0.097 ± 0.006	0.9800	0.24 ± 0.05	0.80 ± 0.06	0.9759	4.8 ± 0.8	0.73 ± 0.04	0.9774

350

351
 352 **Figure 4.** Fitting of the experimental data according to Chick-Watson model (linear portion of the
 353 disinfection curves) and Hom and Weibull models (complete data).

354

355 **3.3. Hydroxyl radical detection**

356 To further study the behaviour observed in the inactivation kinetics of *E. coli*, the generation of the
 357 hydroxyl radical was evaluated by means of p-nitrosodimethylaniline bleaching (Figure 5).

358
 359 **Figure 5.** Degradation of p-nitrosodimethylaniline by hydroxyl radicals generated with visible light in the
 360 absence and presence of catalysts.

361 The amount of hydroxyl radicals generated when no catalyst is used is very low, which is consistent with
362 the behaviour observed in the corresponding control (see Figure 3A). The shape of the curves for both
363 catalysts is very similar, but NZ-Fe showed a slightly higher production of hydroxyl radicals than NZ-Cu
364 (Figure 5). This behaviour is not correlated with the effectivity of NZ-Fe and NZ-Cu photo-Fenton assays
365 suggesting that $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals are not the only mechanism acting in the photo-disinfection process. Since
366 the free radical scavenger could not completely prevent the RNO degradation, there must be other species
367 active in inactivating *E. coli*. In fact, it has been reported that at pH close to neutrality (at which the tests
368 in this work are carried out) and in the presence of hydrogen peroxide, high-valent copper oxide is an
369 active specie [58]. Likewise, another high valence species in the case of iron (ferryl ion; FeIV) can also act
370 at neutral pH as an oxidizing species with high efficiency [59].

371 372 3.4. *E. coli* inactivation studies with leachate of the catalysts

373 To find out if the metal released from the catalyst is responsible or plays a role in the inactivation of *E. coli*,
374 experiments were performed where the water resulting from the disinfection test (after sterilization) was
375 re-injected with the bacteria and a new photo-Fenton process was performed without the addition of
376 catalyst. The results show that the iron leached from the catalyst practically does not inactivate the
377 bacteria (Figure 6). This indicates that only the iron exchanged in the zeolite participate in the production
378 of ROS. In the case of copper both, the exchanged cation and the leached cation are involved in the
379 photocatalytic process. However, it can be noted that the inactivation of *E. coli* is different when copper is
380 in solution, as an initial delay in the curve is observed, although the detection limit is reached at a slightly
381 shorter time. Finally, it is important to remark that even though copper is lost during the photo-Fenton
382 process, the lifetime of the catalyst is not compromised for at least 3 treatment cycles, as discussed above.
383

384
385 **Figure 6.** Inactivation of *E. coli* by photo-Fenton under visible light using the leachate of the catalysts. DL
386 (detection limit) = 50 CFU/mL.

387
388
389

390 **Conclusions**

391 This work has shown that the natural zeolite clinoptilolite exchanged with Fe or Cu (NZ-Fe and NZ-Cu), is a
392 good heterogeneous photo-Fenton catalyst for bacterial inactivation, without the need to add other
393 catalysts. The performance of this modified zeolite was validated by its ability to inactivate *E. coli* in water,
394 reaching the detection limit and without observing bacterial regrowth, demonstrating for the first time
395 the high efficiency of this type of catalysts for water disinfection by heterogeneous photo-Fenton
396 reactions. DR-UV-Vis measurements indicated that both materials possess adequate band gap energies to
397 absorb visible light, ensuring high efficiency under solar radiation. Although NZ-Fe produced more hydroxyl
398 radicals and less leachate, NZ-Cu showed faster kinetics and superior reusability over three disinfection
399 cycles, probably due to a higher copper leachate and the potential presence of the bactericidal effect of
400 high-valence copper oxide. In conclusion, natural clinoptilolite with incorporated metals, due to their low
401 cost and advantageous physicochemical properties, could be employed as sustainable catalysts for
402 heterogeneous photo-Fenton based disinfection, particularly in water treatment applications. Further
403 experimental research will explore the treatment of complex water matrices and economical assessment
404 of the entire treatment compared with standard AOPs.

405

406 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

407 **P. Prieto-Laria:** Investigation, Validation, **P. Fernández-Ibáñez:** Conceptualization, Writing – review and
408 editing, **A. Rabdel Ruiz-Salvador:** Funding acquisition, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing –
409 review and editing, **I. Canosa:** Methodology, Resources, Supervision, **A. Flores:** Resources, Supervision, **C.**
410 **Salameh:** Investigation, Validation, **José Enrique Domínguez-Santos:** Investigation, Validation, **M.**
411 **Ballesteros:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Resources,
412 Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing, **T. Farías:** Conceptualization, Formal
413 analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Visualization,
414 Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing.

415 **Declaration of competing interest**

416 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that
417 could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

418

419 **Data availability**

420 Data will be made available on request.

421

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427

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